

An Effective Framework for Chinese Syntactic Parsing

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Abstract—This paper presents an effective framework for Chinese syntactic parsing, which includes two parts. The first one is a parsing framework, which is based on an improved bottom-up chart parsing algorithm, and integrates the idea of the beam search strategy of N best algorithm and heuristic function of A* algorithm for pruning, then get multiple parsing trees. The second is a novel evaluation model, which integrates contextual and partial lexical information into traditional PCFG model and defines a new score function. Using this model, the tree with the highest score is found out as the best parsing tree. Finally, the contrasting experiment results are given.

Keywords—syntactic parsing, PCFG, pruning, evaluation model.

I. INTRODUCTION

Chinese syntactic parsing is one of the significant components in natural language processing. The simplest and safest way is to do exhaustive bottom-up parsing, and then selects the totally correct parsing tree from all the possible trees. However, because of the ambiguous characteristics of natural language, it is a prevalent phenomenon that one sentence has thousands of possible parsing trees. An exhaustive parsing is often impractical or impossible [1].

In recent years, with the development of large scale of Chinese tree-bank, the Probabilistic Context Free Grammar (PCFG) has become the mostly commonly used method to disambiguate trees. Researchers have presented many algorithms with PCFG to get the best parsing tree, such as best-first algorithm and A* search strategies [2], etc. Most of the algorithms aim to obtain the unique tree with the highest PCFG probability (Viterbi tree). However, as to Chinese, the Viterbi parsing tree is not totally correct in many situations.

There is an example in Fig. 1.

Above phenomenon is caused by the unreasonable assumption of PCFG. For Chinese, the two basic principles of PCFG – the independence assumption and context-freeness assumption – are questionable. So, the additional lexical and contextual information are necessary, which will be discussed in section two.

Above all, although the result of pure PCFG is not satisfying,

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yet it can be used to do initial disambiguation in parsing and get multiple trees. Then a context-sensitive model is used to reevaluate all the trees and choose the best one.

Fig. 1 An Example

This paper is based on this idea. Our framework includes two parts. The first one is a parsing framework to get multiple parsing trees, which is based on an improved bottom-up chart parsing algorithm, and integrates the idea of the beam search strategy of N best algorithm [3], [4] and heuristic function of A* algorithm into pruning, but still guarantee optimality. The second is a novel evaluation model, which integrates contextual and partial lexical information into PCFG model and defines a new score function. The tree with the highest score is found out as the best parsing tree.

Finally, experiments show that our framework is effective.

II. OUR APPROACH

A. The overall description

The original input for the system is the text that has been processed by the word segmentation and part-of-speech (POS) tagging system, such as $T = w_1 / t_1 w_2 / t_2 \dots w_n / t_n$. Through processing of parsing and disambiguation module, finally the best result tree is got, as shown in Fig. 1. This tree can best describe the syntactic structure of the original sentence.

The process of this system can be shown as Fig. 2:

Fig. 2 Flow Chart of the System

The preprocessing module mainly takes use of the indication information of Chinese punctuations to decompose long compound sentences into several single sentences, and simplify the parsing of some sentences that include some special punctuation. For example, the “《” and “》” always indicate that

there must be a name of a book between them, so it can be parsed as a noun phrase (NP). Therefore, a syntax-pattern can be defined as follows:

$NP \rightarrow \langle X \rangle$, X stands for any input text strings.

Similar laws are discovered, so a syntax-pattern set is constructed. This part is not the emphasis of our discussion in this paper, and we will give particular description in other paper. The later two modules will be explained detailedly in next two sections.

B. The parsing and pruning module

This module includes two parts: parsing algorithm and pruning strategy.

1) The Improved Chart Parsing Algorithm

The basic parsing algorithm in our system is an improved bottom-up chart-parsing algorithm, which is presented by Bai Shuo et al. [5]. The algorithm makes reference to GLR algorithm, by introducing a kind of effectual "look ahead" function at low cost to avoid creating lots of useless arcs. Therefore, an inverted role list and a starting rules list are constructed first based on the input PCFG rules. Please refer to [5]-[7] for details.

In their approach, edges that can't lead to the root node S (successful parsing) are filtered out and the searching space and time can be reduced greatly. However, all rules are given the same priority, which can be modified in our approach with PCFG. In our approach, some modifications are made to the lists. The two lists are sorted according to the probabilities of corresponding rules, which ensure more possible parsing path with higher priority. With the proposed modifications, the searching can be heuristic in later parsing process.

2) Pruning strategy

Our approach refers to the beam search strategy of N best algorithm with some variations. N best algorithm keeps only a portion of the edges with higher figure-of-merits (FOMs) compared to other edges in the same cell. But our approach reserves all edges with different POS tags in the same cell. To edges with the same POS tags in the same cell (they have ambiguous sub-trees), no more than N best ambiguous sub-trees can be reserved and others are pruned. The heuristic function of A* algorithm and two thresholds are defined here.

In A* algorithm, the edges are ordered based on a heuristic function, which is the sum of their known internal costs of construction and a conservative estimate of their costs of completion [2]. Formally, for edge e , $cost(e)$ denotes the valuation of e , $\alpha(e)$ denotes the internal cost of construction and $\beta(e)$ denotes the estimate of cost of completion.

$$cost(e) = \alpha(e) + \beta(e) \quad (1)$$

The grammar projection estimate is used because the context information is helpful to select the most possible parsing path before creating corresponding edges. Only the parent context information is considered here.

For edge e shown in Fig. 3, $\alpha(e)$ and $\beta(e)$ are defined as:

$$\alpha(e) = Insidecost(X) = \max\{P(X_1), P(X_2), \dots, P(X_n)\} \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \beta(e) &= Outsidecost(X) \\ &= Insidecost(Y) + Insidecost(Z) + \log P(A \rightarrow XYZ) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Fig. 3 Structure of edge e

Where $\alpha(e)$ is defined as the logarithm probability of the best inside parse of edge e (its Viterbi inside score), and $\beta(e)$ is defined as the outside cost of edge e in given context.

For example, a simple PCFG G and an input sentence S are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1
 EXAMPLES OF A PCFG AND AN INPUT SENTENCE

A Simple PCFG G:

Rule	Probability (P)
S \rightarrow dj	0.497356
S \rightarrow zj	0.224409
dj \rightarrow vp a	0.000495
dj \rightarrow np a	0.006841
vp \rightarrow v n	0.055620
np \rightarrow v n	0.000884
zj \rightarrow dj w	0.342163

An input sentence S:
 工作/v 方法/n 好/a . /w

Fig. 4 shows a chart graph in the parsing process.

Fig.4 A chart graph in the process of parsing

The graph shown in Fig. 4 can be transformed into the tree structure as Fig. 5:

Fig. 5 Tree structure

For edge e_1 in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5, it has only one sub-tree. So it is the Viterbi sub-tree. The root node of the sub-tree is edge e_1 , which is composed of $v[0,1]$ and $n[1,2]$, and edge e_2 is

similar. Given next edge $a[2,3]$, $cost(e_1)$ and $cost(e_2)$ can be computed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha(e_1) &= Insidecost(vp[0, 2]) \\ &= Insidecost(v[0, 1]) + Insidecost(n[1, 2]) + \log P(vp \rightarrow v n) \\ &= \log(1) + \log(1) + \log(0.055620) = -1.254769 \\ \beta(e_1) &= Outsidecost(vp[0, 2]) \\ &= Insidecost(a[2, 3]) + \log P(dj \rightarrow vp a) \\ &= \log(1) + \log(0.000495) = -3.305395 \\ cost(e_1) &= \alpha(e_1) + \beta(e_1) = -4.560164 \\ cost(e_2) &= \alpha(e_2) + \beta(e_2) = -5.218428 \end{aligned}$$

For $cost(e_1) > cost(e_2)$, the branch node $dj[0,3]$ has two ambiguous sub-trees, and the sub-tree including edge e_1 is Viterbi sub-tree. The classical A* algorithm only reserves edge e_1 in this situation. However, here the sub-tree including edge e_2 , instead of e_1 , is the correct sub-tree. Our approach reserves these two sub-trees.

When there are many ambiguous sub-trees, a proper threshold should be defined to combine with heuristic function to prune. The valuations of all such edges are computed and sorted, then edge e_n can be cut if it meets condition: $cost(\max\{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n\}) - cost(e_n) > PROB$, (It means that $cost(\max\{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n\}) / cost(e_n) > 10^{PROB}$).

PROB is defined as a dynamic threshold. It decreases by an invariable value with the increase of the level of the branch node in the tree. PROB of branch node X is defined as follows (the data in (4) are given experimentally):

$$PROB = \begin{cases} 6.0 - level(X)/2, & level(X) \leq 8 \\ 2.0 & level(X) > 8 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Another threshold N is defined to restrict the maximum number of ambiguous sub-trees for every branch node. Number N is defined as 7, which is given experimentally.

C. The evaluation module

Traditional PCFG is based on two basic assumptions:

- 1) Context-freeness assumption, which means that the score of a parsing tree is decided only by its sub-trees and the grammar rules used currently.
- 2) Independence assumption, which means that the sub-trees of one parsing tree are independent to each other and all the sub-trees are independent to the grammar rules.

Based on the two assumptions, the score function is defined as follows: For a tree T which is produced by such a grammar rule: $r : T \rightarrow u_1 u_2 \dots u_n$, the score function of T is:

$$S(T) = P(r) \times \prod_{i=1}^n S(u_i) \quad \Pi \quad (5)$$

As we have said before, the above two assumptions are questionable. The analysis and corresponding resolution are

discussed detailedly in next two sections.

1) Construction of Co-occurrence matrix

Assumption 1) is wrong because the context-sensitiveness of Chinese is obvious. There are some Chinese function words that have important indication to sentence structure.

For example, in Chinese, structural auxiliary “的” is the mark of attribute [8]. That's to say that the probability that there is a noun phrase (NP) behind “的” is much higher than any other phrases such as verb phrase (VP) etc. Considering the phrase “我们的研究计划”: “研究计划” can be a NP or a VP, but because of the anterior “的”, obviously it is a NP. However, in PCFG, without considering the indication of “的”, the “研究计划” will possibly be parsed as a VP, because the probability that “研究” as a verb is higher than that of a noun.

In order to solve this problem, a terminal (POS tag of word) co-occurrence matrix and a non-terminal (phrase or syntax tag) co-occurrence matrix are defined to integrate the context sensitive information into PCFG. In the tree structure, the terminals constitute leaf nodes (e.g. v and n in Fig. 5), the non-terminals constitute branch nodes (e.g. dj and vp in Fig. 5).

Formally, they are defined as follows:

The letter t denotes the terminal.

The letter P denotes the non-terminal.

The backward co-occurrence probability $B(P, t)$ denotes the probability that there is a t immediately before P .

The forward co-occurrence probability $F(P, t)$ denotes the probability that there is a t immediately after P . So,

$$B(P, t) = P(tP / P), F(P, t) = P(Pt / P) \quad (6)$$

Two special marks named b and e are added into the model, which denote the beginning and end marks of a sentence separately. So,

$$B(P, b) = P(bP / P) \quad (P \text{ appears at the beginning of sentence})$$

$$F(P, e) = P(Pe / P) \quad (P \text{ appears at end of sentence}) \quad (7)$$

Obviously, to all P , such unitary condition should be satisfied:

$$\sum_{t'} B(P, t') = \sum_{t''} F(P, t'') = 1 \quad (8)$$

Similarly, the definitions of terminal t are as follows:

$$B(t, t') = P(t't / t), F(t, t'') = P(tt'' / t)$$

$$B(t, b) = P(bt / t), F(t, e) = P(te / t)$$

$$\sum_{t'} B(t, t') = \sum_{t''} F(t, t'') = 1 \quad (9)$$

For all t and P , their B and F values are computed, then the terminal and non-terminal co-occurrence matrixes are constructed. When computing the scores of parsing trees, the two matrixes are used in later formula to contribute to the evaluation of sentences. Thus, the context co-occurrence information is added into our model.

2) New evaluation formula

Assumption 2) is questionable because sub-trees can't

always be independent to each other. So using formula (5) to compute the score of trees is not reasonable. In addition, the product of all the probabilities of sub-trees is lower than that of any sub-tree. A fairly low probability sub-tree will greatly reduce the product. In other words, the result only reflects the low probability events. So, some modifications are made to the score function of (5).

The most difference is that the evaluation score of the parsing tree is the geometric mean of all probabilities but not the product of them.

Formally, for the terminal node t , the terminal before t is t' , the one after t is t'' , score of t is defined as follows:

$$S(t) = \sqrt{B(t, t')^2 + F(t, t'')^2} \quad (10)$$

For the non-terminal node P , which has been deduced by such a rule $r : P \rightarrow u_1 u_2 \dots u_n$, the terminal before P is t' , the one after P is t'' . So, score of P is defined as follows:

$$S(P) = \sqrt{P(r)^2 + \sum_{i=1}^n S(u_i)^2 + B(P, t')^2 + F(P, t'')^2} \quad (14)$$

III. EXPERIMENT RESULTS

Our experiments are performed based on TCT973 Chinese tree-bank (<http://www.chineseldc.org/index.htm>), which is built from true Chinese text corpus after 1990th with manifold styles.

Firstly, 8600 sentences were chosen randomly from the tree-bank as train set, and other 500 sentences as test set. The 2706 PCFG rules used in our system are extracted from the train set, and the corresponding probabilities are computed by using Maximum Likelihood Estimate (MLE) method. The two co-occurrence matrixes are also constructed based on the train set and computed by using MLE method. In addition, some Chinese function words which have special functions are tagged with special marks, such as structural auxiliary “的”、“地”、“得” and tense auxiliary “了”、“着”、“过” etc.

To test that our model has an advantage over PCFG, we do two groups of contrasting experiment.

The first experiment parses the 500 sentences of test set. The lengths of these sentences are between 5 and 40 words with the average length 22.8 words. The standard PARSEVAL measures [9] are used to evaluate the two models, the results are shown in Table 2:

TABLE 2
 RESULTS USING STANDARD PARSEVAL MEASURES

Model	LP (%)	LR (%)	CBs	OCBs (%)	≤2CBs (%)
PCFG	74.8	73.1	1.86	33.6	67.6
Our model	78.2	76.9	1.80	36.9	69.3

Above contrasting results show that our model is superior to traditional PCFG model.

The second experiment selects all the sentences whose lengths are between 5 and 20 from the 500 sentences of test set. This is still an opening test. The results are shown in Table 3:

TABLE 3
 ACCURACY OF WHOLE SENTENCES OF TWO PARSING APPROACHES

Model	Number of sentence	Including correct sentences	Inclusion ratio	Number of correct sentences	Accuracy
PCFG	192	167	87%	116	69.5%
Our model				133	79.6%

In table 3, the “including correct sentences” are the numbers of sentences which include the correct tree in the multiple result trees, and the “inclusion ratio” is the percentage of them. The percentages of 87 prove that our parsing algorithm including pruning is effective. The accuracy shows the disambiguation ability of the evaluation model. It can be seen that disambiguation ability of our model is superior to PCFG.

But the results in table 3 are based on the sentences with middling or short lengths. When dealing with long ones, the results are not so good. Which maybe caused by following reasons. Firstly, by analyzing long sentences, especially those compound ones, we found that even if most of the single sentences in the compound sentences are correct, only one wrong single ones can make the whole sentences wrong. So the inclusion ratio is low. Besides, with the increase of sentences length, there will be much more ambiguous result trees, and to disambiguate is much more difficult. In a word, Chinese syntactic parsing is still a difficult task.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we present an efficient framework for Chinese syntactic parsing. Two main modules are included – a parsing and pruning module and a disambiguation module. The latter is a disambiguation model, which integrates contextual and partial lexical information into traditional PCFG model. Contrasting experiments show that the disambiguation ability is improved.

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